

A Pre-Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Knowledge Regarding Awareness of POCSO Act Among Adolescent Girls 16-18 Years in a Selected School at Abhanpur, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: Background of the Study: The POCSO Act, 2012 is a comprehensive law to provide for the protection of children from the offences of sexual assault, sexual harassment, and pornography, while safeguarding the interest of the child at every stage of the judicial process by incorporating child-friendly A pre-experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding awareness of POCSO Act among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur, Chhattisgarh. The aim of this study was to enhance the knowledge of adolescent girls regarding awareness of POCSO Act. In this study establish three objectives, first is to assess the pre-test and post test knowledge score regarding awareness of POCSO Act among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur Chhattisgarh. Second objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on the knowledge regarding awareness of POCSO Act among adolescent girls (16-18 year) in a selected school at Abhanpur Chhattisgarh. Third objective is to find out the association between pre-test knowledge score regarding awareness of POCSO Act with their sociodemographic variables among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur, Chhattisgarh. The research approach used for the study was quantitative research approach with pre-experimental research design and, research setting is Higher secondary school Abhanpur, target population is adolescent girls 16-18 years using non-probability purposive sampling techniques, sample sizes 60 were selected, formulate the self-questionnaire nine socio-demographic, and fourteen content, and tool validated by seven experts, method of data collection by self-structured questionnaire, and data analysis by used descriptive and inferential statistics, in this study finding reliability of tool used karlpearson's test and re-test method reliability is 0.84 which indicate perfect reliability, The findings of the study revealed that there was marked increased in the post-test knowledge The post-test mean score was 19.23 and the pre-test mean score was 13.13 mean difference is (6.1) Score, it reflects the structured teaching programme was effective. Hence it is concluded that overall post-test mean knowledge score (19.25) is greater than overall pre-test knowledge score (13.13) and after structured teaching programme POCSO Act gain 15.25 of the knowledge. It showed that the "t" value is 11.17 was greater than

the table value 3.46 at ($p < 0.001$) level of significance, which shows the effectiveness of structured teaching programme in which calculated value was χ^2 test. On applying chi-square test demographic variable family monthly income and occupation of father and number of family members as the chi-square value 38.49, 14.66, 9.55 were greater than table value 12.59 at 0.05 level significance respectively. Hence hypothesis H2 was accepted regards to variables. i.e., family monthly income occupation of father number of family members.

Keywords: POCSO act, Child sexual abuse, Sexual harassment, Sexual assault.

1. Introduction

Child sexual abuse is a widespread phenomenon with life-long consequences on the physical and mental health of the child. India has highest prevalence of CSA cases, and the incidence is increasing day by day. The POCSO act defines a child as any person below the age of 18 years and applies to all cases of sexual assault viz, penetrative sexual assault, non-penetrative sexual assault, sexual harassment and use of a child for pornography. However, in the existing system, the students and practicing doctors are not methodically trained about various aspects of CSA relevant to the medical fraternity ie, diagnosis, rational treatment evidence collection, documentation of injuries and treatment of the child Many are not aware of the subtle injuries and psychological impact resulting from CSA. The lack of knowledge may subject many children to repeated victimization. The newly adopted POCSO ACT, 2012 deals with all forms of sexual abuse on children and lays down the principles to handle the child in a systematic manner, protocols to be followed by individuals and hospitals for examination and treatment of the child, the way

judicial proceedings are to be carried out and is the most elaborate law about this problem. However not many people including medicos are aware of provisions of the law.

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Table 1

S. No.	Assessment	Mean	Mean %	SD	Mean Difference	Knowledge Gain%
1.	Pre-Test	13.13	32.82%	4.94	6.1 (19.23-13.13)	15.25% (48.07%-32.82%)
2.	Post-Test	19.23	48.07%	5.45		

2. Material and Methods

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge of POCSO act awareness. The data analysis was carried out based on the objectives and hypothesis set by the investigator. Statal analysis is method for rendering of qualitative information, meaningful and intelligible. Without the aid of statal data collected in research project would be little more than a chronic mass of numbers, statistic procedures enable the researcher to reduce, summarize, organize, evaluate, interpret, and communicate numeric from.

This study presents the analysis and interpretation of data collected from 60 students from higher secondary school students that evaluate the knowledge regarding POCSO act awareness among higher secondary school students from girls higher secondary school, Abhanpur using the self-structured tools the data was collected, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted according to the objectives of the study.

3. Results and Discussion

The first objective is to assess the pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding awareness of POCSO ACT among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur Chhattisgarh.

The finding shown that in pre-test 24(40%) had poor knowledge, 30(50%) are average knowledge and 6(10%) are good knowledge 0(0%) excellent knowledge regarding POCSO act. Whereas in post-test, 42(70%) had average knowledge, and 13(21.67%) good knowledge, 5(8.33%) excellent knowledge regarding POCSO act.

The Second objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on the knowledge regarding awareness of POCSO act among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur, Chhattisgarh.

The findings shown that the mean percentage of pre- test knowledge score is 32.82% and post-test knowledge score is 48.07%, show the analysis of overall knowledge score between pre-test and post-test, post-test mean knowledge score 19.23 is greater than overall pre-test knowledge score 13.13 and after structured teaching programme students 15.25% of the knowledge gain, Mean difference is 6.1 score the difference between pre-test and post –test knowledge score is large and it

is statistically significant.

The third objective is to find out the association between pre-test knowledge score regarding awareness of POCSO act with their sociodemographic variable among adolescent girls 16-18 years in a selected school at Abhanpur Chhattisgarh.

From the above results and discussion clearly stated that there was not significant association of pre test knowledge of adolescent girls 16-18 years with their selected demographic variables like age, religion, number of siblings, type of family, source of information related to POCSO act awareness programme. There was significant association of demographic variables such as family monthly income of POCSO act, occupation of father, number of family members awareness of POCSO act. From the above discussion it was concluded that the structured teaching has better effect among adolescent girls 16-18 years regarding POCSO act.

4. Conclusion

This paper presented a pre-experimental study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding awareness of POCSO act among adolescent girls 16-18 years.

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